

DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGIES AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Pulatova Gulmira Ismoilovna

teacher of technology,

secondary school No. 34,

Pakhtachi district, Samarkand region

Annotation: *In the 21st century, which is called the age of information and technology, the development of science, the creation of innovations in all spheres of life - industry, construction, chemistry, agriculture, textiles, machinery and others - is vital. This process is now recognized in all countries of the world on the path of development. In our country, too, special attention is paid to this process and it is important.*

Keywords: *information technology, technology, development, thinking, information, integration, digital technologies, networks, internet, ideas, electronics, programmers.*

Human society has evolved since its inception. They distinguish three stages of human development. The first stage came at the end of the 19th century, and it was the agrarian stage - it was based on the predominance of agriculture and manual labor on the land. The twentieth century was an industrial stage, and now most of the labor was done by machinery, equipment and tools, and the rich of that time were industrialists and bankers, namely Ford and Rockefellers.

The 21st century will be the information age, and the economies of already developed countries have moved to the field of digital information technologies and electronic services. Now the rich are e-shop owners and information technology programmers.

Today's rich and wealthy countries do not earn money from growing cotton, raising chickens and growing peppers. Today, the sphere of activity of the rich and the rich states and peoples is high technology. Technology creates thinking. Contemplation develops in a society where thought has become. Thoughts are turned by the press and other media.

Here are today's rich people: the high-tech Waltons have \$ 130.59 billion (Uzbekistan's three-year budget of \$ 33 million), and Bill Gates (the owner of Microsoft, a computer programmer) has \$ 91.9 billion. that's more than Uzbekistan's two-year GDP, Jeff Bezos - \$ 80.92 billion (owner of Amazon, owner of The Washington Post and publishing house), Mark Zuckerberg - \$ 61.92 billion (Facebook invented),

Larry Page is worth \$ 34.2 billion, Sergey Brin is worth \$ 43.35 billion (these two people created the Google search engine), Jack Mann is worth \$ 26.7 billion (owner of Alibaba Group) ... There are 2,200 billionaires in the world, with a fortune of more than \$ 9 trillion.

Based on the purpose of the article, we have identified the following tasks.

1. Development of information technology and IT;
2. Humanity is closely linked to information technology;
3. Development of science for development;
4. Information economy of developed countries;
5. A unique achievement of the technical age.

We see that today capital is circulating in the field of information technology, and sometimes the mental labor of one or two people is more effective than the movement of entire states, the hard labor of peoples. A state that claims to be integrated into the world opens the way to thinking, that is, it allows freedom of speech and thought, liberates the press.

In today's economy, the main place is occupied by information technology and IT. Does Uzbekistan have a role in this development and where will it be? All efforts should be focused on this. Increasing the yield from 30 quintals per hectare to 40 or 50 quintals, increasing the amount of irrigated land, raising chickens, etc., will not significantly boost the economy.

Digital economy - online services based on digital technologies, electronic payments, e-commerce, Internet advertising, Internet banking, Internet games, crowdfunding.

The 21st century is the age of information technology. It is in this century that unprecedented new inventions in the field of information and communication have emerged and are developing. The Internet has a special place among the ever-evolving and renewing industries.

Experts have found that in ancient times it took years, even centuries, for inventions to come to life. For example, while it took 150 years for a washing machine and 50-70 years for a car to become a necessity for people, social networks and virtual communications have come a long way in less than a year. .

Of course, in a sense, this may be a unique achievement of the technical age. But the other side of the issue is thought-provoking. It's no secret that the fact that access to the Internet is becoming more convenient and cheaper is "relieving" many people. Including terrorists and saboteurs. It is these individuals who have turned the Internet into their ideological weapon. The saddest thing is that in the past, they used to instill their hateful ideas in people through war, weapons or similar means, but today, they are hooking thousands and millions of people into their hooks in a matter of minutes via the internet.

In our view, as the information age changes rapidly and modern technology develops, members of society also continue to be shaped by circumstances and circumstances. As the President said in his speech, "Currently, most of the services are provided through information technology. The effectiveness of other areas also depends on it."

It is no secret that today everyone is closely connected with information technology. The world is living in a new era of information. In the context of globalization, the idea that "Whoever possesses information, possesses that world" is increasingly becoming a social reality. Nowadays, everyone can easily and quickly connect to the Internet via mobile phones or computer networks. It is as if the universe has become virtual.

Nowadays, the process of informing is increasing by the second with fast pictures, you can easily find any information without difficulty, if you look for useful information, it is good, but ideologically empty and propagating evil, contrary to our national mentality. What if you find yourself in a world of destructive, useless information? How do you avoid this. The internet is not like an international spider web in vain, you can't pull yourself out once you fall into its trap.

Unfortunately, the "electronic world" is being used by various political forces as their main weapon in carrying out their terrorist, extremist propaganda and ideas, propagating their views to the public, and carrying out the activities of every criminal gang. The fact that the major negative forces are creating their own ideological platforms on the Internet, carrying out widespread information terrorism - "electronic jihad" on the Internet, new threats and problems to global and regional security - is creating information security problems in the world.

Any field of science is useful only if it develops in connection with the environment and society, and is integrated with them. Otherwise, it becomes a useless science. So is information. It should be aimed at the benefit of the people.

The computer has a definite and definite role in the collection, storage, processing and practical application of information - regardless of its type and appearance.

The presentation meeting held on June 8, 2020 under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev was also dedicated to this issue, namely, the development of information technology and the digital economy. The meeting set the task to open at least 100 training centers on digital technologies in all regions. It is planned to organize short-term training courses on the basics of programming, e-commerce and graphic design.

Also, at the meeting on April 28, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government," in which the Prime Minister called for the quality implementation and coordination of tasks. the position of advisor was introduced.

Most importantly, the first phase of the One Million Programmers project covered more than 62,000 students, 5,400 of whom were issued certificates of competency and stressed the need to further accelerate the training of modern programmers, despite the quarantine conditions.

The development and implementation of smart devices is also used in our schools, for example, smart bells and various sensors that measure room temperature. In addition, we can create modern training rooms depending on the seismic detection device, photoelectric converter device, thermoelectric converter device. The use of cloud technologies in data storage has become very useful.

It will be useful for the student to be active and not distracted in the classroom, and the quality of education will increase. In this process, we propose the following:

- Introduce modeling technologies into the teaching process due to the lack of imagination of students in the educational process;
- Virtually create a workflow and display the results in cases where the practical use of technical equipment in the classroom is not possible;
- analysis on the basis of modeled objects;
- Demonstration of chemicals;
- In geography lessons, maps and models of cities can be used effectively.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the introduction of high information technology in various spheres of society is a requirement of the times. Of course, young people should take advantage of such huge changes in the field of information technology. Having a high level of technical faith facilitates the process of labor, production, technology takes on tasks that are complex and difficult for man, and opens a wide way for human mental activity, facilitates. Communication with the peoples of the world will be easier and faster. It should not be forgotten that its result will serve the development of the country.

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